

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: EKWULUO****FIRST NAME: CELESTINE****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: PROF. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Why is it crucial to categorize sources into primary, secondary, and tertiary?

- To confuse researchers
- To complicate the research process
- To conduct research effectively¹**
- To limit access to information

2. How should researchers evaluate the reliability of sources?

- Based on personal opinions
- By looking for peer-reviewed materials²**
- By only using Google search results

¹ Turabian Kate, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition, revised by Wayne Booth, Gregory Colomb, Joseph Williams, Joseph Bizup, William FitzGerald (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 36-37.

² Ibid., 37-41.

- By avoiding reputable scholars
3. Why is it important to cite your sources in academic writing?
- To hide the original creators of information
- To make your writing more confusing
- To acknowledge the sources of your information³**
- To avoid giving credit to others
4. Which citation style is widely used in the humanities and some social sciences?
- APA style
- Harvard style
- MLA style
- Chicago or Turabian style⁴**
5. What is the purpose of bibliographies in academic writing?
- To confuse readers
- To indicate the breadth of research and assist readers in using sources⁵**
- To hide sources
- To exclude all cited works
6. Why is crafting research questions important in a dissertation?
- To ensure specificity and relevance⁶**
- To confuse readers

³ Turabian Kate, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition, revised by Wayne Booth, Gregory Colomb, Joseph Williams, Joseph Bizup, William FitzGerald. (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 139.

⁴ Ibid.,

⁵ Ibid., 155.

⁶ Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Maria Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth Edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2019), 61-94.

- To make the study abroad
 - To limit adaptability
7. What is the pivotal role of the dissertation prospectus?
- Serving as a cover page
 - Acting as a complete blueprint for the dissertation⁷**
 - Providing a final conclusion
 - Advocating for marketing purposes
8. How should doctoral candidates integrate quantitative and qualitative research methods?
- Independently
 - Without acknowledging biases
 - By understanding the combined utility of both approaches⁸**
 - By focusing solely on one method
9. Why is transparency vital in qualitative research?
- To ensure trustworthiness and credibility⁹**
 - To confuse participants
 - To hide biases
 - To facilitate data analysis
10. What essential elements are included in a dissertation concept paper?
- Problem statement, research questions, research design¹⁰**

⁷ Sampson P. James, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition (Tallahassee: Educational Psychology and Learning Systems Faculty Publications, 2017), 3.

⁸ Ibid., 7-9.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth Edition, 133-200.

¹⁰ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition, 2-5.

- Introduction, literature review, methodology, references
- Variables, measures, hypotheses
- Acknowledgments, abstract, discussion

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Maria Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth Edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2019.

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Tallahassee: Educational Psychology and Learning Systems Faculty Publications, 2017.

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